

NONLINEAR THERMAL AND MECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF EDGE EFFECTS
IN $[\theta/(\theta-90^\circ)]_s$ LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

A family of $[\theta/(\theta-90^\circ)]_s$ Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic laminates have been analysed for their thermo-mechanical free edge effects using a quasi-three-dimensional finite element analysis with initial stress iteration for material nonlinearity. The laminates were assumed to be stress free at a curing temperature of 132.2°C (180°F) and was cooled to the room temperature of 20°C . Initial thermal stresses resulted in the laminates and were reported. The laminates were then subject to a uniform applied strain in the longitudinal direction of the laminate until failure occurred according to a maximum strain failure criterion. Results were obtained for $\theta = 0^\circ, 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 75^\circ$ and 90° . Initial thermal stresses were found in all laminates. In particular, the free edge initial thermal stresses were very high. However, these initial thermal stresses were found to be favourable to the failure strength of the laminate. A comparison was made between the present results and those of $[\theta/-\theta]_s$ laminates from a separate paper. It was found that, for loading in the longitudinal direction and with initial thermal stresses included, the $[\theta/-\theta]_s$ laminates were generally stronger than the $[\theta/(\theta-90^\circ)]_s$ ones and the $[45/-45^\circ]_s$ laminate was the strongest amongst all laminates.

KEYWORDS: $[\theta/(\theta-90^\circ)]_s$ laminates; Thermal effects; Edge effects; Nonlinear; Initial stresses.

1. INTRODUCTION

For a composite lamina, the thermal expansivity in the transverse direction to the fibres is higher than the longitudinal one. During the manufacturing process, composite laminates are usually cured at temperatures much higher than their design operating temperatures. It is a normal practice to stack up the plies in various fibre orientations to enable the laminate to withstand a general loading

pattern. When this effect is coupled with the mismatch in expansivity in fibre axis directions in the laminate, initial thermal stresses and strains result when these laminates are cooled down from their curing temperature. These initial thermal stresses and strains also change with the laminate ply orientations. By ignoring the initial stresses, previous investigators [1-8] have shown that a finite-width laminate exhibits very high interlaminar stresses at the free edge under uniform axial strain loading. Since the initial thermal stresses can have a very great impact on the response of laminates under loading, a thermal and mechanical analysis of edge effects in $[45^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$ and $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ laminates was carried out, and was reported in a previous paper [9]. In this reference, composite laminates made up from Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) were used. The resin layers between the plies in the laminate were modelled in the analysis. Also, a quasi-three-dimensional isoparametric finite element and an initial stress iteration method were used to tackle the problem of material nonlinearity. The initial thermal stresses of a laminate were first obtained by noting that after curing the laminate was cooled from its stress free temperature of 132.2°C (180°F) to the room temperature of 20°C . Then a uniform axial strain was applied to the laminate and the interlaminar stresses were calculated. The uniform axial strain was then increased in steps until the laminate exhibited failure according to a maximum strain failure criterion. The present work is based on the method in [9] and extends the investigation to cover a range of $[\theta/(\theta-90^\circ)]_s$ laminates.

FIGURE 1. Problem Definition

A separate analysis was carried out in [10] with the same method in [9] for the family of $[\theta/-\theta]_s$ laminates. The strength of the $[\theta/-\theta]_s$ and $[\theta/(\theta-90^\circ)]_s$ families of laminates are compared in this paper.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE FREE EDGE PROBLEM

Consider the long, symmetric laminate shown in Figure 1. It has four plies, each of thickness h and width $2b$, and is loaded with a uniform axial strain $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ in the x -direction. Away from the ends the displacements u , v , w in the x , y , z , directions respectively in any $x = \text{constant}$ plane can be assumed to be [2]:

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y, z) &= x\bar{\epsilon}_x + U(y, z) \\ v(x, y, z) &= V(y, z) \\ w(x, y, z) &= W(y, z), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where U , V and W are functions of the coordinates y and z only.

The displacement field of equations (1) should satisfy the equations of equilibrium and the stress free conditions on the edges, $y = \pm b$, and the top and bottom surfaces, $z = \pm 2h$.

3. FORMULATION

The formulations of the quasi-three-dimensional finite element and the initial stress iteration method which are used in the present study have been formulated in a previous paper [1]. The inclusion of thermal effects is now outlined [9].

In one dimension, the coefficient of thermal expansion, α , of a solid at temperature T in $^\circ\text{C}$ is defined by

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{l} \frac{dl}{dT}, \quad (2)$$

where l is the original length of the solid. According to [11], over limited temperature ranges, the thermal expansion of most solids increases with temperature and can be represented by equations of the form

$$\alpha = a + bT + cT^2 \quad (3)$$

where a , b and c are constants. Equations (2) and (3) can be combined to give, in one dimension, the strain increment $\Delta\epsilon$ resulting when the temperature changes from T_1 to T_2 :

$$\Delta\epsilon = \frac{dl}{l} = \int_{T_1}^{T_2} (a + bT + cT^2)dT = \left[aT + \frac{bT^2}{2} + \frac{cT^3}{3} \right]_{T_1}^{T_2}. \quad (4)$$

The lamina principal thermal strains can then be written in terms of the form of (4). After transformation the thermal strain vector, $\Delta\epsilon_{xyz}$, with respect to the x , y and z coordinates can be found. Now using $\underline{\epsilon}^\circ$ and $\underline{\epsilon}$ to denote the total

strain and the mechanical strain vectors respectively, we have

$$\underline{\epsilon}_{xyz} = \underline{\epsilon}_{xyz}^{\circ} - \underline{\Delta}\epsilon_{xyz} \quad (5)$$

When the above formulation is incorporated into the finite element formulation a global thermal force vector is formed. These forces are in addition to the mechanical boundary forces exerted on the laminate. Then the total strains in each finite element are calculated in the normal way to obtain the mechanical stresses and strains.

For the nonlinear solutions the initial stress iteration method is then applied. This will give a better stress-strain state in the laminate than a usual linear analysis can provide. A maximum strain failure criterion is now defined. A laminate is considered to have failed if any value of strain in the laminate, either in the laminae or the resin layers, has reached its corresponding ultimate value. In a lamina the ultimate values of strains are [1]:

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_{11u} &= 0.014 \\ \epsilon_{22u} = \epsilon_{33u} &= 0.008 \\ \epsilon_{ij u} &= 0.065,\end{aligned}$$

where $i, j = 1, 2, 3, i \neq j$. The ultimate values of tensile strain, ϵ_{Tu} , and shear strain, ϵ_{Su} , in the resin layer are [1]:

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_{Tu} &= 0.2 \\ \epsilon_{Su} &= 0.8.\end{aligned}$$

The initial stress iteration analysis is repeated until the laminate fails according to the maximum strain failure criterion.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Due to symmetry, it is only necessary to analyse the top right hand corner of the laminate cross-section shown in Figure 1(b). So the mesh shown in this figure was used for the analysis of the $[\theta/(\theta-90^{\circ})]_s$ laminates, where $\theta = 0^{\circ}, 15^{\circ}, 30^{\circ}, 45^{\circ}, 60^{\circ}, 75^{\circ},$ and 90° . In the present arrangement a resin layer is modelled between the $\theta/(\theta-90^{\circ})$ plies. The nonlinear CFRP lamina and resin stress-strain relationship given in [1] were included. Referring to Figure 1(c), the top surface of the lower of the two resin layers is defined as the $(\theta-90^{\circ})$ /resin interface. It was shown that the interlaminar stresses along this interface and the free edge stresses were important indicators for laminate stress-strain response [1,9]. So these stresses are now presented.

For all cases the laminates were cooled from the assumed stress free temperature of 132.2°C of the CFRP material to the room temperature of 20°C . The same stress free temperature was used in [9]. The drop in modulus due to temperature

change in the present case is small and is neglected.

The relationship between the thermal expansion and temperature in the transverse direction of a CFRP lamina is expressed in the form of equation (4) and contains coefficients a , b and c with the following values:-

$$\begin{aligned} a &= 30.847 \times 10^{-6} \\ b &= 8.9095 \times 10^{-9} \\ c &= 0.12057 \times 10^{-9}. \end{aligned}$$

These constants were used for the transverse direction as well as the through thickness direction of the lamina. Since the material properties of a lamina in the transverse direction are dominated by the behaviour of the resin used for the lamina, it is reasonable to use the same constants of thermal expansion for the resin. Along the longitudinal direction of a lamina, the thermal expansion is reported to be practically zero [12]. So longitudinally, $a = b = c = 0$.

The initial thermal stress-strain patterns were obtained using the relationship for the thermal expansion as well as the nonlinear material relationship used in [1]. The laminates were then loaded with a uniform axial strain $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ in the x -direction until failure occurred. When this happened the nonlinear stress-strain response was obtained.

4.1 Initial Thermal Stresses In Table 1 the initial thermal stresses of the seven laminates for all six components of stresses along the $(\theta-90^\circ)$ /resin interface are presented for cooling from 132.22°C to 20°C . Three values are presented for each combination of laminate stacking sequence and stress component. On the LHS of each group of values the initial thermal stress in the main part of the laminate is presented while the maximum and minimum values inside the laminate along the same interface are also given on the RHS of these values. The top number is the maximum while the bottom number is the minimum. In general, the stress components along the θ /resin interface have values smaller than the corresponding ones along the present $(\theta-90^\circ)$ /resin interface.

The thermal expansion of all laminae is practically zero in the fibre longitudinal direction but the expansivity transverse to the fibre direction is non-zero, so initial thermal stresses exist. Referring to the $\theta = 0^\circ$ case in Table 1, when cooled, the laminae inside the laminate only contract in the direction transverse to the fibres and an internal strain in the x -direction results in the laminate. Although this strain of 0.3×10^{-3} is quite large, the σ_x stress in the main part of the laminate is only about 25.0 MPa. However, in the region near the free edge, the σ_x stress varies and reaches a very high value of 52.7 MPa, as shown by the maximum value in Table 1. The σ_x stress for laminates with different values of θ is also varied. In particular, a high compressive stress of -89.8 MPa is obtained for $\theta = 90^\circ$. The σ_y stress in the

main part of the laminate increases with θ , as opposite to the case of the σ_x stress. The σ_z stress is zero except in the free edge region where its magnitude becomes large. The σ_{yz} shear stress is also zero except in the free edge region, where the values of shear stress become varied. The σ_{xz} stress is zero in the main part of the laminate. Its value increases along the interface towards the free edge for the angle-ply laminates. The σ_{xy} stress exists only for angle-ply laminates. It varies moderately in the free edge region.

θ	σ_x		σ_y		σ_z		σ_{yz}		σ_{xz}		σ_{xy}	
0°	25.0	52.7 23.0	-7.0	131.8 -30.2	-0.1	53.6 -2.9	0.0	0.0 -19.8	0.0	0.0 0.0	0.0	0.0 0.0
15°	22.6	51.9 19.7	-4.5	104.3 -24.8	-0.1	45.1 -2.4	0.0	0.0 -17.9	0.0	18.3 0.0	8.1	13.1 -25.2
30°	16.4	42.7 11.8	1.7	46.8 -11.7	-0.1	23.5 -1.2	0.0	0.0 -12.3	0.0	28.0 0.0	13.9	19.7 -23.8
45°	8.3	15.1 -1.0	10.1	12.2 -12.4	0.0	1.2 -8.3	0.0	3.1 0.0	0.0	0.1 -3.3	15.6	15.6 3.7
60°	0.6	2.2 -22.4	17.5	17.6 -10.2	0.1	1.1 -15.5	0.0	7.7 -2.5	0.0	29.0 0.0	13.4	14.8 -9.3
75°	-4.0	0.2 -61.1	23.0	23.0 -6.6	0.2	1.7 -25.1	0.0	12.9 -1.2	0.0	19.8 0.0	7.6	13.9 6.2
90°	-3.7	0.6 -89.8	25.1	25.1 -3.1	0.2	1.9 -28.1	0.0	14.7 -0.8	0.0	0.0 0.0	0.0	0.0 0.0

TABLE 1 Initial thermal stresses in MPa in the main part of the $[\theta/(\theta-90^\circ)]_s$ laminates along the $(\theta-90^\circ)$ /resin interface: top & bottom numbers on the RHS are the maximum & minimum values along the interface respectively.

4.2 Thermal and Mechanical Stresses After cooling, the laminates were subject to an applied $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ strain until failure occurred according to the maximum strain failure criterion. The $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ laminate failed at $\bar{\epsilon}_x = 0.0063$. Failure occurred in the 90° laminae. The strain transverse to the fibres exceeded its maximum allowable value. It was observed that after cooling the resulting $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ strain was only about -0.0003. When an axial strain was applied, the resulting strain $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ in the laminate became 0.0063, as shown in Table 2. The second column of this table is the initial thermal $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ strain and the third column is the final iterated strain $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ after the application of an axial strain in the x-direction. So the applied strain in the fourth column is obtained by subtracting the initial

thermal strain in the second column from the iterated strain in the laminate in the third column. After nonlinear iteration the failure value of 0.0080 was reached in the direction transverse to the fibres in the 90° layers.

θ	initial thermal $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ strain ($\times 10^{-6}$)	final initial & mechanical $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ strain ($\times 10^{-6}$)	Applied $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ ($\times 10^{-6}$)
0°	-296	5 976	6 272
15°	-344	6 839	7 183
30°	-428	9 298	9 726
45°	-467	15 666	16 133
60°	-424	8 882	9 306
75°	-342	6 835	7 177
90°	-297	5 975	6 272

TABLE 2. Comparison of $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ in $[\theta/(\theta-90^\circ)]_s$ laminates

Same as the 0° case, the failure modes of the other six laminates, namely those with $\theta = 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 75^\circ$ and 90° were all in the direction transverse to the fibres inside the laminae. Also, the initial thermal $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ strains were all negative. This had an effect to provide a higher applied $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ strain at failure. For all laminates, the initial thermal strains were favourable to the laminate failure applied strain.

Failure of the $[15^\circ/-75^\circ]_s$ laminate occurred inside the -75° layer in the central part of the laminate, close to the -75° /resin interface. The failure applied strain of 0.0072 was slightly higher than that of the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ laminate.

The failure applied strain of the $[30^\circ/-60^\circ]_s$ laminate was 0.0097 and was higher than those of the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ and $[15^\circ/-75^\circ]_s$ laminates. Failure occurred inside the -60° layer at the free edge.

The $[45^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$ laminate failed at an applied strain of 0.0161. The 45° layer exhibited failure at the free edge at this applied strain. For details on the analysis of this laminate, see [9].

The applied $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ strain at failure of the $[60^\circ/-30^\circ]_s$ and $[75^\circ/-15^\circ]_s$ laminates were 0.0093 and 0.0072 respectively, as shown in Table 2. Failure occurred inside the 60° and 75° layers for the two laminates respectively at the free edge.

The $[90^\circ/0^\circ]_s$ laminate had a failure applied strain of 0.0063. Same as the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ laminate, failure occurred in the 90° lamina.

An analysis on the $[\theta/-\theta]_s$ laminates was carried out in [10] with the same method

for the $[\theta/(\theta-90^\circ)]_s$ laminates in the present paper. Part of the results are presented in Table 3. It is interesting to see in this figure that the all 90° laminate has about the same strength as some other $[\theta/-\theta]_s$ laminates, after the initial thermal stresses have been taken into account. A premature failure was detected in the $[15/-15]_s$ laminate, due to shear failure in the 15° layer near the free edge. At this position the ϵ_{13} shear strain, with respect to the fibre material axes, exceeded its maximum allowable value. When comparing the two sets of results in Tables 2 and 3, it can be seen that the applied $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ strains at failure for the $[\theta/-\theta]_s$ laminates are generally higher than those in the present $[\theta/(\theta-90^\circ)]_s$ ones. This indicates that, after taking into account of the initial thermal stresses, the $[\theta/-\theta]_s$ laminates are stronger than the $[\theta/(\theta-90^\circ)]_s$ laminates with respect to an applied strain in the x -direction.

θ	initial thermal $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ strain ($\times 10^{-6}$)	final initial & mechanical $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ strain ($\times 10^{-6}$)	Applied $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ ($\times 10^{-6}$)
0°	-8	14 954	14 962
15°	154	8 498	8 344
30°	378	11 804	11 426
45°	-467	15 666	16 133
60°	-2 302	9 012	11 314
75°	-3 392	7 841	11 233
90°	-3 680	7 721	11 401

TABLE 3. Comparison of $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ in $[\theta/-\theta]_s$ laminates

The free edge thermal and mechanical stresses of the $[15^\circ/-75^\circ]_s$ and $[75^\circ/-15^\circ]_s$ laminates at failure are shown in Figures 2(a) and 2(b) respectively. As expected, the dominant stress components of the laminates in these figures are σ_x and σ_y . The σ_{xy} shear stress and the σ_z 'peel' stress of the $[15^\circ/-75^\circ]_s$ laminate near the resin/ -75° interface are quite high in magnitude, as shown in Figure 2(a). The stress distributions of the $[30^\circ/-60^\circ]_s$ laminate are very similar to those of the $[15^\circ/-75^\circ]_s$ ones. The σ_x and σ_y stresses of the $[75^\circ/-15^\circ]_s$ laminate are also very large, as shown in Figure 2(b). The free edge σ_z stresses of this laminate are highly compressive, as opposite to the case of the $[15^\circ/-75^\circ]_s$ laminate. The stress distributions of the $[60^\circ/-30^\circ]_s$ laminate are very similar to those of the $[75^\circ/-15^\circ]_s$ laminate. The free edge stresses of the $[45^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$ laminate are smaller than the last two cases, although at a very high applied strain [9]. The free edge stresses of the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ and $[90^\circ/0^\circ]_s$ laminates are smaller than those of the previous cases.

(a) $[15/-75]_s$ laminate

(b) $[75/-15]_s$ laminate

FIGURE 2. Free edge stress distributions of $[15/-75]_s$ and $[75/-15]_s$ laminates at failure applied $\bar{\epsilon}_x = 0.0072$

5. CONCLUSIONS

A family of $[\theta/(\theta-90^\circ)]_s$ angle-ply laminates for $\theta = 0^\circ, 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 75^\circ,$ and 90° have been analysed for their thermal and mechanical behaviour using a quasi-three-dimensional iso-parametric finite element. This analysis was based on the method formulated in previous papers [1,9]. The nonlinear initial stresses

resulting from cooling from the stress free temperature of 132.2°C to the room temperature of 20°C in the laminates were found. All laminates were then subject to an applied axial strain in the x -direction until failure was detected inside the laminate. This analysis include the material nonlinear behaviour of the lamina. A maximum strain failure criterion was used so that a laminate was considered to fail when any lamina or resin layer inside the laminate had principal material strain exceeding its ultimate value. The laminates were taken as CFRP plates and their nonlinear material properties were based on those in [1]. The drop in modulus of the laminates due to temperature change is small and was ignored in the analysis. However, the thermal expansivity of a CFRP lamina varies with temperature by an appreciable amount and was included. The stresses inside the laminate at failure were given.

It was found that although some of the initial thermal stresses in the laminates were very high, they had an effect to increase the laminate failure applied strain in the x -direction. Also, the $[\theta/-\theta]_s$ laminates were generally stronger than the $[\theta/(\theta-90^{\circ})]_s$ ones with respect to the present loading pattern and the $[45^{\circ}/-45^{\circ}]_s$ laminate was the strongest amongst all laminates.

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